

Investigations on the Kinetics and Mechanism of Polarographic Reduction of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-Nitroacetanilides in Aqueous Ethanolic Medium

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Polarographic behaviour of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitroacetanilides in aqueous ethanolic solutions has been studied as a function of pH using NaNO₃ (0.1 M) and Triton X-100 (0.001%) as the supporting electrolyte and maxima suppressor, respectively with a view to investigate the kinetics and mechanism of the reduction of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitroacetanilides at d.m.e. The reduction of the depolarizers has been found diffusion-controlled and irreversible. The potential-dependent rate constant, $k_{f,h}$, has been calculated by Koutecky's method at different pH and the values of kinetic parameters (αn_a and $k_{f,h}^0$) have been calculated from $\log k_{f,h}$ vs $E_{d.e.}$ plots which are linear thereby indicating that only a single rate-determining step is involved in the electrode process of each depolarizer. Based on the values of αn_a and the variation of $E_{1/2}$ with pH, the stoichiometry of the rate-determining step involved in the reduction of each depolarizer at d.m.e. has been established. A tentative mechanism for the polarographic reduction of each depolarizer has been postulated.

THOUGH several workers¹⁻²⁴ have studied the polarographic behaviour of aromatic nitro compounds, viz., nitrobenzene, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitrochlorobenzene, nitrotoluene, nitrophenol, nitrobenzaldehyde and nitrobenzoic acid as a function of pH of buffers and also as a function of different experimental conditions, reports on the polarographic behaviour of nitroacetanilides are sparse. Runner and Wagner²⁵ studied the polarographic reduction of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitroacetanilides in absolute ethanol buffers and reported that the depolarizers were reduced in a single 4-electron step. The easier reduction of the *ortho* isomer was attributed to the intramolecular structure (chelation) of this compound. Literature however reveals that studies on kinetics and mechanism of polarographic reduction of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitroacetanilides are still lacking. With this end in view the present study has been undertaken.

Experimental

o-, *m*- and *p*-Nitroacetanilides were B.D.H. products and were recrystallized from ethanol before use. The other chemicals were of B.D.H., A.R. grade. The concentration of each depolarizer (in 25% aquo-ethanolic solution) was maintained at 1.0×10^{-3} M. Desired concentrations of various constituents of B.R. buffer for a desired pH value were added to the solution to be polarographed. Sodium nitrate (0.1 M) was used as a supporting electrolyte. A manual polarograph (Toshniwal CLO2) in conjunction with a polyflex galvanometer (Toshniwal PL 50) was used. All the measurements were made at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. Purified nitrogen was used

for removing dissolved oxygen. The potentials were measured against a saturated calomel electrode (SCE). The number of electrons, n , involved in the reduction of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitroacetanilides was determined by millicoulometric method of DeVries and Kroon²⁶. Having known the value of n , Ilkovic equation was used to calculate the value of D , the diffusion coefficient of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitroacetanilides at the various pH values of B.R. buffer. The potential dependent rate constant, $k_{f,h}$, was calculated by Koutecky's method^{27,28}. The kinetic parameters αn_a and $k_{f,h}^0$ were calculated from the plots of $\log k_{f,h}$ vs $E_{d.e.}$. Throughout the measurements the current at the end of the drop (i.e., the maximum current) was recorded for the reasons given by Meites^{29(a)}. The d.m.e. had the following characteristics: $m = 2.77$ mg/sec; $t = 2.92$ sec; $m^{2/3}t^{1/6} = 2.385$ mg^{2/3} sec^{-1/6} (in 0.1 M NaNO₃, open circuit); $h_{corr} = 56.2$ cm.

Results and Discussion

o-, *m*- and *p*-Nitroacetanilides yield well-defined waves at different pH values of B.R. buffer. The reduction of the *ortho* isomer takes place in two steps at low pH values (≤ 3.30). The same is true for the *meta* isomer at pH 2.00. Millicoulometric studies reveal that the first step corresponds to a 4-electron reduction process while the second one to a 2-electron process. In all, 6 electrons are involved in the overall reduction process at lower pH values. At higher pH values (> 3.30) the *ortho* and *meta* isomers are reduced in a single step corresponding to a 4-electron reduction process,

while the *para* isomer is reduced in a single step involving 4 electrons over the entire pH range (2.00 to 11.20).

The wave-heights of all the steps are diffusion-controlled for all the isomers at different pH values of B.R. buffer as evidenced by the fact that i_d vs $h_{\text{corr}}^{1/2}$ plots are linear and pass through the origin.

The various criteria^{29(b),30,31} of ascertaining the irreversibility of an electrode process were applied to the present systems and it was found that the polarographic reduction of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitroacetanilides in different steps was totally irreversible.

Kinetics and mechanism of polarographic reduction of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitroacetanilides: It is well known² that the aromatic nitro compounds are reduced at d.m.e. in a 4-electron step to a phenylhydroxyl amine derivative. In an acid medium the phenylhydroxylamine derivative is reduced further to an amine in a separate wave. In an alkaline medium, depending upon the strength of the base, the phenylhydroxylamine derivative is stable to further reduction but may, under the influence of the alkali, form condensation products which are electroreducible. Based on the above frame work and also on the values of the kinetic parameters of the irreversible electrode reactions of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitroacetanilides, a tentative mechanism can be put forward for the polarographic reduction of these isomers.

Kinetics of electrode reactions of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitroacetanilides has been studied as a function of pH (B.R. buffer). The plots of $\log k_{r,h}$ vs $E_{1/2}$ at different pH values are linear. This shows^{32,33} that there is only one rate-determining step involved in the electrode reaction of each isomer. The values of kinetic parameters (αn_a and $k_{r,h}^0$) for both the reduction steps have been listed in Tables 1, 2 and 3.

An attempt to estimate n_a (the number of electrons involved in the rate-determining step) for the 1st step apparently leads to a conclusion^{32,34} that

TABLE 1—VALUES OF POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND KINETIC PARAMETERS (αn_a AND $k_{r,h}^0$) FOR THE ELECTRODE REACTION OF *o*-NITROACETANILIDE AT DIFFERENT pH VALUES OF B.R. BUFFER IN 25% (v/v) AQUO-ETHANOLIC SOLUTIONS AT 25 ± 0.1°

pH	i_d μA	$-E_{1/2}$ V (SCE)	Slope mV	$D \times 10^6$ cm ² /sec	αn_a	$k_{r,h}^0$ cm/sec
2.00	I step	14.08	0.242	80	3.94	0.82 8.04×10^{-4}
	II step	5.76	0.942	190	3.63	0.29 3.14×10^{-7}
3.00	I step	12.80	0.353	81	—	0.64 5.38×10^{-6}
	II step	8.00	1.240	188	—	0.27 1.94×10^{-6}
4.10		13.12	0.380	81	3.88	0.62 3.25×10^{-6}
5.00		12.80	0.458	90	3.69	0.60 4.96×10^{-6}
6.10		13.12	0.492	75	3.88	0.80 2.49×10^{-7}
7.00		12.80	0.534	70	3.69	0.79 1.04×10^{-7}
7.95		10.88	0.645	70	2.67	0.74 6.53×10^{-9}
8.95		11.52	0.700	93	2.99	0.55 4.02×10^{-9}
10.10		13.12	0.770	90	3.88	0.59 9.61×10^{-9}
11.20		14.40	0.840	72	4.67	0.70 1.03×10^{-10}

TABLE 2—VALUES OF POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND KINETIC PARAMETERS (αn_a AND $k_{r,h}^0$) FOR THE ELECTRODE REACTION OF *m*-NITROACETANILIDE AT DIFFERENT pH VALUES OF B.R. BUFFER IN 25% (v/v) AQUO-ETHANOLIC SOLUTIONS AT 25 ± 0.1°

pH	i_d μA	$-E_{1/2}$ V (SCE)	Slope mV	$D \times 10^6$ cm ² /sec	αn_a	$k_{r,h}^0$ cm/sec
2.00	I step	13.44	0.280	52	4.07	0.82 1.52×10^{-4}
	II step	4.48	0.798	72	—	0.87 5.29×10^{-13}
3.30		13.44	0.400	78	4.07	0.67 1.14×10^{-5}
		13.12	0.445	91	3.88	0.58 7.16×10^{-6}
5.00		13.76	0.520	100	4.27	0.55 2.12×10^{-6}
6.10		13.44	0.570	74	4.07	0.70 9.27×10^{-6}
7.00		11.52	0.625	93	2.99	0.62 6.37×10^{-9}
7.95		13.12	0.720	78	3.88	0.67 7.94×10^{-10}
8.95		12.80	0.780	67	3.69	0.78 8.09×10^{-11}
10.10		12.16	0.800	124	3.33	0.50 1.19×10^{-9}
11.20		12.80	0.800	120	3.69	0.51 1.15×10^{-9}
11.95		13.44	0.810	118	4.07	0.55 4.42×10^{-10}

TABLE 3—VALUES OF POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND KINETIC PARAMETERS (αn_a AND $k_{r,h}^0$) FOR THE ELECTRODE REACTION OF *p*-NITROACETANILIDE AT DIFFERENT pH VALUES OF B.R. BUFFER IN 4% (v/v) AQUO-ETHANOLIC SOLUTIONS AT 25 ± 0.1°

pH	i_d μA	$-E_{1/2}$ V (SCE)	Slope mV	$D \times 10^6$ cm ² /sec	αn_a	$k_{r,h}^0$ cm/sec
2.00	16.17	0.332	60	5.90	0.90	3.33×10^{-5}
3.30	14.17	0.424	63	4.52	0.86	1.83×10^{-5}
4.10	13.40	0.440	68	4.04	0.80	1.10×10^{-6}
5.00	12.94	0.480	72	3.77	0.75	7.80×10^{-7}
6.10	12.47	0.520	68	3.50	0.80	1.41×10^{-7}
7.00	12.32	0.602	65	3.42	0.83	7.20×10^{-9}
7.95	12.78	0.685	69	3.68	0.78	1.17×10^{-9}
8.95	13.67	0.740	72	3.62	0.75	3.94×10^{-10}
10.10	11.86	0.780	76	3.17	0.71	2.83×10^{-10}
11.20	10.78	0.840	78	2.62	0.70	6.82×10^{-11}

n_a is equal to 2 in the case of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitroacetanilides at all the pH values (as the values of αn_a lie in the range 0.50-0.90) because for totally irreversible systems, as the present ones are, α should be less than³⁵ 0.5. However, according to Meites³⁶⁽¹⁾ only a single electron can be transferred at a time during the course of an electrode reaction and hence a value of n_a exceeding 1 should merely mean that successive steps are too nearly simultaneous to be distinguished on the time scale implicit in the polarographic measurements. Similarly, a perusal of αn_a values for the second step shows that n_a can be taken as equal to 1 in the case of *o*-nitroacetanilide and equal to 2 in the case of *m*-nitroacetanilide.

A perusal of $E_{1/2}$ values shows that these get shifted to more negative potentials with an increase in pH. The $E_{1/2}$ vs pH plots for the first step are linear. The value of p i.e. the number of H⁺ ions involved in the rate-determining step, can be obtained from equation (1).

$$\frac{dE_{1/2}}{d(pH)} = \frac{0.05915}{\alpha n_a} \cdot p \text{ (at 25°)} \quad \dots (1)$$

Thus, from the slope of $E_{1/2}$ vs pH plots the value of p can be determined provided that the value of

αn_a is constant throughout the pH range. According to Meites^{29(d)}, the elucidation of the stoichiometry of the rate-determining step associated with a totally irreversible wave must include a demonstration that αn_a is constant and independent of the experimental conditions that are varied. In the present study the experimental condition which is varied is the pH of the buffer. In the present investigation, however, it has been found that αn_a is not constant and that the change in the value of αn_a with pH shows that it is ' α ', the transfer coefficient, which is changing with the change in pH. It thus follows that the change in $E_{1/2}$ may not be entirely due to the change in pH of the medium but may also be due to a change in ' α '. Therefore, a correction in equation (1) to account for the variation in α is necessary. This can be done by considering³⁰ the variation of $\alpha E_{1/2}$ with pH. With this modification equation (1) takes up the form :

$$\frac{d(\alpha E_{1/2})}{d(pH)} = \frac{0.05915}{n_a} \cdot p \text{ at } (25^\circ) \quad \dots (2)$$

It follows from this equation that a plot of $\alpha E_{1/2}$ vs pH should be a straight line with a slope of $-\frac{0.05915}{n_a} p$, and this has actually been observed in the present investigation. In this way the value of p can be obtained since the value of n_a is known. This has been found to be 1.

Having thus established the stoichiometry of the rate-determining step, i.e. $n_a=2$ and $H^+=1$ for the first step of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitroacetanilides and the second step of *m*-nitroacetanilide, and $n=1$ and $H^+=1$ for the second step of *o*-nitroacetanilide in the entire pH range investigated, the following mechanism can be suggested for the polarographic reduction of nitroacetanilides :

First step :

o-, *m*- and *p*-Nitroacetanilides at all pH values :

Second step :

(a) *o*-Nitroacetanilide :

(b) *m*-Nitroacetanilide :

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